

Supplementary irrigation using shallow groundwater for soybean after wetland rice

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We evaluated methods of irrigation using shallow groundwater on soybean grown after rice. A soybean crop growth model (CRPSM) was used to improve irrigation management and phenology clock.

Irrigation methods tested were manual drip, spraying at 5- and 14-d intervals, furrow, and rainfall only. For furrow irrigation, 7.6-cm and 5.0-cm diameter pumps were used.

Soybean cultivar Orba was sown 12 Jul 1985. Rainfall received during the

Rainfall,^a irrigation, and grain yield of soybean under several irrigation methods. Maros, Indonesia, 1985.

Treatment	Supplemental irrigation (mm)	Effective irrigation		Total water supply (mm)	Grain yield (t/ha)		ET actual ^b (mm)	Water use efficiency (t/ha-mm)
		mm	%		Observed	Predicted		
Rainfed	—	0	—	115	0.6	0.7	188	—
Manual drip	165	116	70	231	1.4	1.4	265	8.62
Sprayed every 5 d	233	156	67	271	1.4	1.4	266	6.02
Sprayed every 14 d	233	156	67	271	1.3	1.4	251	5.52
Furrow 7.6 cm pump	274	156	57	271	1.0	1.2	269	3.85
Furrow 5.0 cm pump	274	156	57	271	0.8	1.2	269	2.88

^a Rainfall received was 144 mm. Effective rainfall (115 mm) = 80%. ^b Predicted from model.

cropping period totaled 115 mm. Minimum water consumption was 116 mm.

Manual drip irrigation produced the highest yield, furrow irrigation with the

5.0-cm pump the lowest (see table). The results indicate that soybean yields can be doubled with supplementary irrigation (see figure). □

ERRATA

Influence of P, K, micronutrients, and dolomite on azolla growth, 13:4 (Aug 1988), 23. Soil data in column 1, paragraph 2, lines 2-3 should read “0.113% total P, 0.0155% Olsen P...”

Effect of azolla green manure on rice yield, 13:4 (Aug 1988), 29. Soil data in column 2, paragraph 2, lines 2-3 should read “0.113% total P, 0.0155% Olsen P...”

Grain characteristics of traditional Basmati varieties of northwest India, by V.P. Singh, E.A. Siddiq, F.U. Zaman, and A.R. Sadananda. 13 (5) (Oct 88), 10-11.

Page 11: lines 2-3 should read: “represent group B. HBC-30, 34, 40, 45, 46, 95, 98, and 136; Mohabawali, Kanwali,” . . .